

Studies on the Coagulation of Nickel Hydrrous Oxide Sol

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Bhattacharya and Kumar¹ investigated the relation between the electrolyte concentration, c , and the reciprocal of the corresponding time of coagulation, $1/t$, in the region of slow coagulation and obtained hyperbolic curves in the majority of the cases, but in a very few cases the plots were straight lines. Bhattacharya and Bhattacharya² suggested a relation between the concentration ' c ' of the coagulating electrolyte and the time of coagulation ' t ' of copper ferrocyanide sol in the form of the equation:

$$c = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$$

where a , m , and n are constants. In this communication attempts have been made to verify this equation by the studies on the slow coagulation of nickel hydrrous oxide sol by electrolytes.

Procedure.—Hydrrous oxide sol of nickel was prepared by excessive washing of the freshly prepared precipitate of the hydroxide according to the method of Tiwer and Cook³. The time of coagulation was determined by the visible separation method as described by Bhattacharya and Kumar¹ and Singh and Bansal⁴. Experiments were performed with two different concentrations of the sol, viz., A and A/2, using different electrolytes. The observations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Values of constants ' a ', ' m ', and ' n '.

Conc. of sol A = 1.920 g. of nickel oxide/litre.

Electrolyte used.	a		$*m$		n (min ⁻¹)	
	Sol A.	Sol A/2.	Sol A.	Sol A/2.	Sol A.	Sol A/2.
KCl	4.00	1.00	125.000	125.003	121.250	291.250
K ₂ SO ₄	0.02	0.02	0.238	0.156	0.247	0.170
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.01	0.01	0.090	0.025	0.036	0.030

*The values are in m. moles/litre.

1. *This Journal*, 1951, 28, 179, 638; 1952, 29, 687, 759.
2. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1955, 10, 551.
3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 733.
4. *Kolloid Z. Polymere*, 1963, 189, 149.

The nickel hydroxide sol shows a normal behaviour on dilution, as evidenced by the less amount of the electrolyte required for the diluted sol than for the concentrated one, the time of coagulation being kept constant. The values of the constant 'n' vary normally or abnormally with dilution, specifically with the nature of the precipitating ion. In the case of KCl, the value of 'n' increases with dilution of the sol, whereas with other electrolytes, the values are in decreasing order. It is an established fact that (i) number of particles per ml, (ii) the distance between the particles, and (iii) surface adsorption are the main factors which govern the precipitation of sols by electrolytes. Hence on dilution, the decrease or increase in stability due to the predominating influence of one factor over the other may be responsible for the normal or abnormal variation of the values of 'n', which may be concluded as an index of stability to represent the susceptibility of the sol to the electrolyte.

FIG. 2.

Scale—X-axis: 10 div. = 0.02 (same for all electrolytes),
 Y-axis: (a) 10 div. = 2 m. moles/litre for KCl.
 (b) 10 div. = 2×10^{-2} m. moles/litre for others.

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